

Organizational Trust and Employee Performance in Selected Hotels in Edo State of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The seeming lack of trust between employees and their colleagues prompted this study. The broad objective of the study was to examine the extent of relationship that exists between organizational trust and employee performance in selected hotels in Edo State. The study adopted a Survey Research Design. The population of the study was 326 and the sample size was 180 arrived at using Taro Yamane's Statistical formula. Data was collected through questionnaire and analysed with the aid of Multiple Regression Analysis while the hypotheses was tested using Pearson's Table of Test of Significance. From the result of the analysis, it revealed that interpersonal trust and job satisfaction has a statistically significant positive relationship in selected hotels in Edo State that 97% change in job satisfaction was accounted for by changes in interpersonal trust. Following this result, it was concluded that trust is a very important issue in the industry. It was therefore recommended that the hotels studied should endeavour to employ competent hands to handle the affairs of the organization as this will engender healthy competition among the employees and that they should also encourage honesty and make the employees work in unity as this will make the jobs of the employees more satisfying.

Keywords: Organizational Trust; Interpersonal Trust; Employee Performance and Job Satisfaction.

1. Introduction

Organizations exist to satisfy customers wants; it is in doing this that their survival would be assured. Maximally satisfying their customers either in the form of offering quality services or production of quality goods or both will ensure that they remain vibrant and relevant in the market place. However, central to achieving these dreams of competitive products or services are the employees who are said to be the bedrock of the very existence of any kind of organization. Extant literatures and researchers have come to the conclusion that amongst all the resources organizations possess, that human resource (HR) is the most important of them all. Gabcanova (2011) opines that employees of any organization are its most important assets. Jones and George (2009) posit that one of the most important resources in all organisations is human resources; the people involved in the production and distribution of goods and services. Also aligning with this assertion is Ganesh (2015) who avers that the most precious and important asset among all the asset of any organisation are the employees.

As a result of the importance ascribed to employees by researchers and scholars, a lot of efforts have been put in order to decipher, predict and motivate them to function at their very best. Çelik, Turunç and Begenirbaş (2012) state that the basic concern of behavioural sciences is to understand the behaviours of employees, make future predictions and control employees' behaviours and thus to increase the efficiency of employees and organizational efficacy. This is because the behaviour, actions and inactions of employees have a great role to play in organizations' sustainability and continued existence. Corroborating this, Ebere, Abdurrahim and Yasar (2014) posit that the behaviour, actions and inactions of the

employees play major roles in the realization of the organization's mission, vision, goals and objectives. Their behaviours depend on so many things among which are the level of embeddedness, engagement and participation. Others are the level of trust, motivation, the job itself and satisfaction. In this study however, the major concern is trust and the role it plays in determining the performance of employees in the hospitality industry in Edo State.

Trust has become an important concept in management as a result of its influence on not just the performance of the employees but also of the organization in general. Parastoo and Karimi (2015) opine that the management based on trust is a new expression of old thoughts and its position is observed well in current relations and using its mechanisms can be effective in achieving good individual and organizational results. The presence of trust in the workplace is essential for organizational performance and competitiveness in an increasingly global economy (Lamsa & Pucetaite, 2006). Trust has also been linked to organizational outcomes such as higher sales and profits, lower employee turnover, increased job satisfaction among employees (Davis, Schoorman, Mayer, & Tan, 2000), and increased levels of cooperative behaviour among employees (Gambetta, 1988). Trust is critical to organizational excellence in the 21st century (Shockley-Zalabak, Morreale & Hackman, 2010).

Trust exists in very many facets in life; it could be trust in homes, trust in one's partner, in government or the military. In the context of this study, it is concerned with trust that exists in organizations known as organizational trust (OT). Just like there are variabilities in trust definition, so also are there differences in OT. It is a discrete but concretizing process with behaviours of individuals in an organizational structure in a feeling of accuracy, belief, commitment and sincerity to each other (Arslan, 2009). It is a psychological state providing a feedback of how employees perceive the problems in the situations in which the organization is endangered (Baştug, Pala, Kumartaşlı, Günel & Duyan, 2016). Trust as it exists within an organization can also be categorized further. Koç and Yazıcıoğlu (2011) opine that providing trust in organizations; it is possible to mention three dimensions such as trust in institution, trust in management and trust in colleagues or interpersonal trust.

This study is focused on the hospitality industry which is regarded as one of the fastest growing sector of the Nigerian economy. Bello (2002) posits that the hospitality industry in recent time is reputed to be one of the fastest growing industries in Nigeria. It offers huge amount of employment opportunity to the unemployed, both graduate and non-graduates. The tourism and hospitality industries are one of the world's largest sectors, amounting to 'over 10% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP)' (Cooperatal, 2005), and employing huge numbers of people; 'it employs 8% of the global workforce. This study focused on six hotels in Edo state. The hotels are Randekhi Royal Hotel, Precious Palm Royal Hotel, Uyi Grand Hotel, Yak Hotel, Divine Royal Hotel and Evergreen Garden Hotel Limited. The employees of these organizations seem not to trust the competences of their colleague to help in carrying out a good job and they fear that their colleagues only care for themselves alone. This seems to be affecting the level of satisfaction the employees derive from their jobs. These culminated in the reasons that necessitated this study to identify the place of trust in the performance of employees in the studied firms.

Over the years, organizations appeared to be experiencing crisis that relates to trust in one way or another; the studied hotels in Edo state seem not to be exempted from this. Employees of the hotels studied seem to be viewing the trust conditions in their organization from a negative perspective. The interpersonal trust in the studied firms seems to be low. The employees doubt the competences of their colleagues to do a good job so as to elicit favourable remark from management which could influence reward. They also doubt the sincerity of the intentions of their colleagues to give good report when asked and to care about the wellbeing of fellow workers in the organisation. The atmosphere appears to be fraught with suspicion, betrayal and disloyalty amongst workers. This is seen when employees back-bite each other by telling management what they discussed in secret and deliberately frustrating their colleagues' effort to complete a task. This seems to be affecting the job satisfaction level of employees in the studied firms. As a result of this seeming trust issues and the roles trust have been observed to play in organizations sustainability, this study becomes pertinent to empirically ascertain in practical terms what actually happens in the studied organizations as it relates to trust issues. The hotels chosen are Randekhi Royal Hotel and Precious Palm Royal Hotel from Edo South Senatorial zone, Uyi Grand Hotel and Yak Hotel in Edo North and Divine Royal Hotel and Evergreen Garden Hotel Limited in Edo Central.

The broad objective is to examine the type of relationship that exists between organizational trust and employee performance. Specifically, the study seeks to identify the extent of relationship that exists between interpersonal trust and job satisfaction in selected hotels in Edo State.

What is the extent of relationship that exists between interpersonal trust and job satisfaction in selected hotels in Edo State?

Research Hypothesis

H_a: Interpersonal trust and job satisfaction have a significant positive relationship in selected hotels in Edo State.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Organizational Trust

Trust as a concept has been a topic of concern in so many disciplines over several years. Paliszkievicz (2011) posits that streams of research on trust can be found in the fields of psychology, philosophy, sociology, economics and management. Trust has an extensive amount of literature; however, as a result of it being studied in different disciplines, each of the disciplines has come up with its own unique concepts and definitions. Even within a given discipline, trust could be viewed differently depending on the situation and conditions. Lewicki and Bunker (1995) opine that in fact, even within a given field, there is often a lack of agreement on the definition of trust. It is however worthy to note that despite the differences in opinion with regards to trust, researchers from different discipline have come to acknowledge the importance of trust. Despite the eclectic nature of trust research, researchers from every discipline have acknowledged the value of trust. Trust enables people to live in risky and uncertain situations (Mayer, Davis & Schoorman, 1995). It also provides the means to decrease the amount of complexity in a complex world, by reducing the number of options an individual has to consider in a given situation (Lewis & Weigert, 1985). It has often been argued that trust is essential for successful cooperation and effectiveness in organizations (Lane, 1998; McAllister, 1995; Nooteboom, 2002).

Fukuyama (2000) defines trust as expectations that arise in societies where the members share common norms, behave honestly and cooperate with each other. Yilmaz and Kabadayı (2000) describe trust as the beliefs about the unselfishness of the other party, readiness to risk-taking and dependency at a certain level. Dyer and Chu (2000) view trust as one party's confidence that the other party in the exchange relationship will not exploit its vulnerabilities. In the view of Coote, Forrest and Tam (2003) "...trust exists when one party has confidence in the honesty, reliability, and integrity of their partner". Cohen and Diemhart (2013) opine that trust is a form of strategic behaviour or rational economic decision making in situations that involve risk and vulnerability. From the definitions of trust given thus far, it is clear that trust is an exchange between or among people.

The concept of organizational trust has been approached and defined varyingly, depending on the interests of the scholars and their disciplinary foci (Anheier & Kendall, 2002). Gills (2003) defines organizational trust as the organization's willingness, based upon its culture and communication behaviours in relationships and transactions, to be appropriately vulnerable, based on the belief that another individual, group or organization is competent, open and honest, concerned, reliable and identified with common goals, norms, and values. It is the willingness of the employee(s) to be vulnerable to the actions of the employer(s) based on the expectation that they would act in order to satisfy his needs irrespective of the ability to monitor or control (Onogwu, 2012). Tan (2000) views it as employee's feeling of confidence that the organization will perform actions that are beneficial, or at least not detrimental to him or her. It is the global evaluation of an organization's trustworthiness as perceived by the employee (Hollander Vineburgh, 2010). Vakola and Bouradas (2011) posit that it is the psychological state providing a feedback of how employees perceive the problems in the situations in which the organization is endangered.

2.1.2 Interpersonal Trust

Mcknight, Choudbury, and Kacmar (2002) see interpersonal trust as one party's willingness to depend on the other party with feeling of relative security even though negative consequences are possible. This makes interpersonal trust to be putting oneself at the mercy of the other. Six (2007) posits interpersonal trust is a psychological state comprising the intention to accept vulnerability to the actions of another party, based upon the expectation that the other will perform a particular action that is important to you. Interpersonal trust building is an interactive process in which individuals learn or unlearn to establish and maintain trustworthiness, under given organizational (contextual and structural) settings, and subject themselves to policies directly or indirectly, positively or negatively sanctioning the building of interpersonal trust (Paliszkievicz, 2010). Stable intentions for behaviour can be stimulated by durable policies, structures and contextual settings (Six & Sorge, 2008).

Sonnenberg (1994) opines that trust increases when people are perceived as competent. If employees believe that they can depend on their co-workers to produce a quality piece of work that would affect their job in a positive way, they will be willing to trust the judgment of those competent co-workers. Interpersonal relations can be created, maintained and influenced in organizations. To buttress this point, Six (2007) states that "if an organization's management wishes to promote interpersonal trust-building in the organization, then a combination of three types of organizational policies can be effective".

- a) By creating a culture in which relationships are important and in which showing care and concern for the other person's needs is valued (relationship-oriented culture);

- b) Through normative control rather than bureaucratic control, because acting appropriately is the goal in normative control;
- c) Through explicit socialization to make newcomers understand the values and principles of the organization and how 'we do things around here'.

For successful feedback and observation of advanced organizational behaviour such as more satisfaction in the jobs employee do, a high level of interpersonal trust among the co-workers in organization is needed (Bakiev, 2013). In new era, responding to the basic needs of employees in each organization is a priority and one of the most important needs of employees in organization is establishing trust among them and organization and trust between them and their colleagues (Khanifar, Moghimi, Jandaghi, Gh & Zarvandy, 2009).

2.1.3 Employee Performance

Performance as a term has been generating a lot of controversies from management experts and researchers alike. They have defined performance differently depending on the field or the expertise of the person defining the term. For example, Wade and Richardo (2001) opines that performance is the ability to achieve organizational goals and objectives while Daft (2000) explicates that performance as it has to do with organizations is the organization's ability to accomplish its aims through the use of resources in a properly structured manner. On the other hand, Martineli (2001) posits that performance is a measure of the state of an organization, or the outcomes that results from management decision and execution of those decisions by employees of the organization. This brings to limelight the importance of employees in determining the performance of organizations.

Trust has been found to determine the performance of employees; it has the capability to influence the way and manner employees go about their duties in an organization. It is becoming more and more accepted that trust in the organizations and workplace is a critical factor leading to better employee and organizational performance (Williams, 2003; Nyhan, 2000). Research has revealed that the trust of employees is linked to their working attitudes and behaviours (Aryee, Budhwar & Chen, 2002; Atuahene-Gima & Li, 2002). Studies using experimental methods have also confirmed the influence of trust on individual work performance (Wong, Wong & Ngo, 2002). Trust is so important to performance because it is a critical precursor to those exchanges that are tied to so many performance outcomes (Paliszkievicz, 2012).

Viewing the influential role played by trust in organizations, O'Brien (2001) posits that it increases creativity and critical thinking at the employee level. Reina and Reina (1999) also suggest that employee performance tended to surpass the expectations of management and that workers felt greater freedom to express their ideas when leaders created trusting environments in their organizations. Shockley-Zalabak and colleagues (2000) found that organizations with higher levels of organizational trust were more successful and innovative than institutions with lower levels of trust.

Organizations with higher level of trust amongst the employee and management are expected to have performances that surpass organizations with lower trust in the organization, management and colleagues. Supporting this, Dirks and Ferrin (2001) state that it is expected that with high level trust, it should result in high level business manners (work satisfaction, organizational commitment), positive organizational behaviours (such as organizational citizenship behaviour) and high level performance. Trust allows parties to make themselves vulnerable to such risk with the expectation that positive outcomes will appear (Rousseau, Sitkin, Burt & Camerer, 1998).

2.1.4 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an important predictor of employees performance and by extension, productivity. Galanou et al (2010) posit that the term job satisfaction has become a very significant one, now that managers seek for practices which are likely to make people more satisfied and therefore, more productive. Locke (as cited in Yang and Lee 2009) define Job satisfaction as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences. Smith et al (as cited in Galanou et al, 2010) opine that job satisfaction is the feelings that worker has for his job. Spector (1997) states that whereas the humanitarian perspective views job satisfaction as a reflection of the good treatment of employees, the utilitarian perspective views job satisfaction as an antecedent of positive organisational functioning". The utilitarian school of job satisfaction puts an emphasis on the positive relationship between job satisfaction and higher organisational performance.

Job satisfaction is influenced by the level of trust employees have in their organization and their colleague. Trust has been linked to overall employee job satisfaction and perceived organizational effectiveness (Shockley- Zalabak, Ellis & Winograd, 2000). Various research findings had established the importance of job satisfaction on the achievement of organisational goals. External work factors such as supervisor relations, pay, co-worker relations and organisation culture and trust significantly influence employee satisfaction and commitment to the organisation (Pepe, 2010).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This work is anchored on the **Social Exchange Theory (SET)** which evolved from Thorndike's (1932, 1935) work on the development of reinforcement theory and Mill's (1923) marginal utility theory (Smale, 1990). Modern-day influences have been derived from the work of sociologists such as Homans (1961), Blau (1964) and Emerson (1972). However, the SET have mostly been credited to Blau (1964) which has its origin in the norm of reciprocity earlier proposed by Gouldner in 1960.

The SET is all about exchanges and the norms of reciprocities. SET is based on the premise that human behaviour or social interaction is an exchange of activity, tangible and intangible particularly of rewards and costs. The purpose of this exchange is to maximize benefits and minimize costs (Homans, 1961). In this exchange, people consider the benefits and risks involved in a social relationship between or among them. After this consideration, when they envisage that risks involved outweigh the rewards to be gained, people will likely abandon or end the relationship. It treats the exchange of benefits notably giving others something more valuable to them than is costly to the giver, and vice versa, as the underlying basis or open secret of human behaviour and so a phenomenon permeating all social life (Homans, 1961).

Social exchange between or amongst people are based on trust that the people in an exchange will act accordingly. Blau (1964) states that social exchange relationships are based on trust. That is, when an individual gives to another, they do so trusting that the other party will reciprocate. Therefore, unlike economic exchange, social exchange is not an explicit, contractually based arrangement. Eventually, such relationships evolve over time into trusting, reciprocating, loyal, and mutual relationships (Trivers, 2009). The result of the exchange is mostly left to the discretion of the parties involved. Blau (1964) posits that: "social exchange ...involves favours that create diffuse future obligations, not precisely specified ones, and the nature of the return cannot be bargained about but must be left to the discretion of the one who makes it...Since there is no way to assure an appropriate return for a favour, social exchange requires trusting others to discharge their obligations" (p. 93- 94).

Trust has been observed to be the major ingredient in an exchange relationship. The trust here could be trust in management, the organization, or colleagues which will engender an obligation to reciprocate resulting in better performance by employees in form better job satisfaction.

Empirical Review

Oyibo (2013) investigated the extent to which hospitality industry contributes to the economy in both potential and in real term. Sufficient data was collected, analyzed and tested using the Chi square statistical method out of the 80 sampled stakeholders in the industry. The study found that the hospitality industry contributes veritably to economic development of Nigeria and reshaping of her national image in the Diaspora. It was gathered from the study that a positive correlation exists between the hospitality industry and the GDP of the nation. From the findings the researcher recommended enhanced investment in the sector and provision of adequate infrastructure and enabling environment if the industry's full potentials will be properly harnessed towards economic development of the nation.

Abubakar, Chauhan and Kura (2014) examined the relationship between perceived organisational politics, organizational trust, perceived human resource management practices and employee turnover among Registered Nurses in Nigerian public hospitals using multiple regression analysis technique. One hundred and seventy five Registered Nurses participated in the study. Result indicated that perceived organisational politics was significantly and positively related to turnover intentions. The result also showed that both organizational trust and perceived human resource practices were significantly and negatively related to turnover intentions. Theoretical and practical implications of the results are discussed.

Mohamed, Abdul-Kader, and Anisa (2012) carried out a study whose purpose was to examine the relationship between job satisfaction, organizational trust and organizational citizenship behaviour in India. The data used for the research was from two private banking organizations in Tiruchirappalli District (Sample Size 101) and the method of analysis was correlation. The results revealed the fact that job satisfaction is positively related to organizational trust, affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment.

Olamiposi, Adedeji and Effiong (2015) examined the influence of organizational trust and job satisfaction on teachers' job performance among teachers in Ekiti State Nigeria. Two hundred and fifty eight teachers randomly drawn from Ekiti State public secondary schools participated in the study. Organizational trust scale, Job satisfaction scale and Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale were used as measures of investigation. Four hypotheses were tested using the independent t-test and the two way Analysis of Variance. Results showed that organizational trust significantly influences job performance among teachers in Ekiti State. Also, it was revealed that job satisfaction significantly influences job performance among teachers. However, no significant interaction effect of job satisfaction and organizational trust was found on job performance. Result of data analyses also showed that sex has no significant influence on job performance among teachers in Ekiti State]. It was recommended that teachers should be given responsibilities and authority with less

supervision to boost their sense of belongingness, respect and commitment which sustains trust in organizations and enhance performances.

Aninkan (2014) examined how reward management and job enrichment determine the level of job satisfaction in the job place in Ogun State, Nigeria. A sample of 173 staff was selected using random sampling technique. The responses were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Descriptive Statistics. The findings indicated that there is significant positive relationship between job enrichment and job satisfaction; but a negatively significant relationship between reward management and job satisfaction. It was concluded that employees at the Ogun State Polytechnics are motivated more by what Herzberg called intrinsic factors than hygiene factors. It was recommended that there should be regular training of staff to enhance or increase the number of skills that individuals use while performing the job.

Parastoo and Fariba (2015) aimed to investigate the structural model between organizational trust and organizational silence with job satisfaction and organizational commitment of the employees of Islamic Azad University of Isfahan, (Khorasgan) branch Iran. The study method was descriptive-correlation. The study population was the employees of Islamic Azad University of Isfahan branch (Khorasgan) as 340. 180 employees were selected by simple random method and sampling Table. Data was collected through administration of questionnaire. Pearson correlation coefficient and structural equations modelling were applied in the analysis. The results of study showed that organizational trust had inverse and significant relation with organizational silence and had positive and significant relationship with job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Also, there was an inverse and significant relationship between organizational silence and job satisfaction and organizational commitment. The results of structural equations modelling showed that organizational trust had direct impact on organizational silence, organizational commitment and job satisfaction and has indirect impact via organizational silence on organizational commitment and job satisfaction. Also, organizational silence had direct impact on organizational commitment and job satisfaction.

The lacuna spotted in literature is that Hotels in Edo State have not been examined to determine the type of relationship that exists between organizational trust and employee performance. This is a big gap because there are a plethora of Hotels in Edo state which contributes significantly to the economy of the state and studying Trust in the Hotels to see how it influences performance will go a long way in boasting the performance of the Hotels which will have a trickle-down effect on the economy of the state.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted Survey Research design because the study seeks to examine the type of relationship that exists between the variables of the study. To do this, opinions of employees in the focused organizations will be sampled through the use of a structured questionnaire, evaluated and analyzed. This makes Survey Research design the most appropriate design to be adopted in this study.

The population of the study consist of 326 employees in the studied firms.

Taro Yamane's Statistical formula was used to determine the sample size of the study which is 180 employees. The formula is given below as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+(Ne)^2}$$

Bowley's formula was used to allocate the questionnaire in proportion to the population of the selected firms. The formula used is given below as:

$$nh = \frac{nNh}{N}$$

Data used in the study was elicited through primary source; questionnaire instrument will be used in this regard. The instrument that was used is questionnaire that is structured in a Five point Likert format. The coding used are: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Disagree (3), Strongly Disagree (2) and Undecided (1).

The instrument used was subjected to scrutiny by validators using content and face validity test. After much correction, they certified that it was fit for the study.

Spearman-Brown's Split-Half technique was adopted for this purpose and the result obtained is shown below:

Table 1: Reliability Test Table			
Reliability Statistics			
Cronbach's Alpha	Part 1	Value	.732
		N of Items	9 ^a
	Part 2	Value	.721
		N of Items	8 ^b
	Total N of Items		
Correlation Between Forms			.727
Spearman-Brown Coefficient	Equal Length		.843
	Unequal Length		.843
Guttman Split-Half Coefficient			.794
Source: Field Survey, 2018 Computation: SPSS ver. 20			

The result obtained from the reliability table above shows that the instrument is reliable because it (.843) is more than the threshold of acceptance which is .7.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

The multivariate nature of the variables of the study influenced the decision to use Multiple Regression Analysis.

4.1 Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 2: Collation of Responses and Mean							
S\N	Questionnaire Items	SA	A	D	SD	UD	X
	Interpersonal Trust						
1	My co-workers are good at their jobs.	27	31	30	26	12	3.28
2	I believe my colleague in the organization can do their jobs properly.	27	29	28	30	12	3.23
3	The other workers in my organization have the necessary skills to execute their duties well	19	29	35	26	17	3.06
4	My colleagues do not know how to do their jobs well except they are supervised.	24	29	45	20	8	3.33
5	We do not lie against each other in my organization.	21	27	32	22	24	2.99
6	I believe my colleagues will tell the truth about me when they are asked.	16	30	31	24	25	2.90
7	I am confidence that what I discuss with my colleague will not be leaked to the organization.	24	26	34	24	18	3.11
8	We tell the truth about issues in my firm.	22	34	33	19	18	3.18
9	We care for each other in my organization.	27	22	40	25	12	3.21
10	I believe that my colleagues in my organization will not do things that will affect me negatively.	30	26	27	29	14	3.23

11	We normally protect ourselves in my organization.	22	20	59	14	11	3.22
12	There is elements of jealousy in my place of work.	30	46	28	13	9	3.60
Job Satisfaction							
13	I will enjoy my work more if my co-workers know how to do their jobs well.	27	60	27	9	3	3.79
14	I get frustrated when I am assigned duties to do with others because they delay me as a result of not having enough skills to do it.	25	35	31	33	2	3.38
15	I enjoy my stay in the organization because we are truthful in my organization.	24	42	30	23	7	3.42
16	I am confidence about my job and happy to stay in the organization because my colleagues will come to my aid when things start getting difficult for me.	21	43	25	24	13	3.28
17	We enjoy our duties because we behave like brothers and sisters in the organization.	31	32	36	19	8	3.47

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Regression for Interpersonal Trust and Job Satisfaction

Table 3: ANOVA Output (ANOVA ^a)						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3677.785	3	1225.928	1204.069	.000 ^b
	Residual	124.215	122	1.018		
	Total	3802.000	125			
a. Dependent Variable: JOBSAT						
b. Predictors: (Constant), CFOTHERS, HONESTY, COMPT						

Table 4: Coefficient Output						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.704	.320		8.463	.000
	COMPT	.741	.154	.656	4.828	.000
	HONESTY	-.005	.105	-.004	-.044	.965
	CFOTHERS	.387	.130	.334	2.967	.004
a. Dependent Variable: JOBSAT						

Table 5: Regression Result

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.984 ^a	.967	.967	1.009	.208
a. Predictors: (Constant), CFOTHERS, HONESTY, COMPT					
b. Dependent Variable: JOBSAT					
Source: Field Survey, 2018					

Table 3 reveals that 97% change in the dependent variable (Job Satisfaction) is accounted for by changes in the independent variables (Concern for Others, Honesty and Competence) as indicated by the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .967$). It is also revealed from the table as shown by the r coefficient that a positive and high relationship exists between the dependent and independent variables ($r = .984$).

4.2 Test of Hypothesis

H_a: Interpersonal trust (Competence, Honesty, and Care for Others) and job satisfaction has a significant positive relationship in the selected hotels in Edo State.

Table 7: Test of Significance for Hypothesis Three

N	Cal. r	DF	Crit. r.	Verdict
126	.984	124	0.178	Significant
Source: Field Survey, 2018.				

Table 4 shows the result of the test of significance carried out on interpersonal trust and job satisfaction in the selected Hotels in Edo State. From the table, it shows that at 5% level of significance and 124 degrees of freedom, that the critical r is .178 while the calculated r is .984. From the result, it is shown that the calculated r is greater than the critical r, it is therefore concluded that the relationship existing between the variables is statistically significant.

5.1 Discussion of Findings

From the test of hypothesis which states that interpersonal trust and job satisfaction have a significant positive relationship in the selected hotels in Edo State, it was revealed that a 97% change in Job Satisfaction is accounted for by changes in interpersonal trust and that the relationship existing between the variables is statistically significant. This implies that interpersonal trust (trust in colleagues at work) significantly influences the level of satisfaction the employees will get from discharging their duties at work. The result indicated that the more employees trust the competences of their colleague, trust their honesty and believe in their genuine concern for others, the more the employees will be relaxed in carrying out their duties which will metamorphose into a satisfactory work experience as shown by the analysis. These finding align with the study of Olamiposi, Adedeji and Effiong (2015) who examined the influence of organizational trust and job satisfaction and showed that organizational trust significantly influences job performance among teachers in Ekiti State. Also aligning with the findings of this study is that of Mohamed, Abdul-Kader and Anisa (2012) that carried out a study to examine the relationship between job satisfaction, organizational trust and organizational citizenship behaviour. The results indicated the fact that job satisfaction is positively related to organizational trust, affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment.

From the test of hypothesis, it was revealed that 97% change in Job Satisfaction is accounted for by changes in interpersonal trust and that the relationship existing between the variables is statistically significant.

5.2 Conclusion

On the strength of the findings of the study, it is concluded that trust is a very important issue in the organization as it has the potential of determining and influencing the performance of the organisation. Organization trust seems to be an antecedent of organizational performance in hotels, Edo State of Nigeria. Job or work activities experienced at either the

employees or organizational level is associated with employee trust. From the findings it was established organizational trust and employee satisfaction have significant individual influences on the job performance of the studied hotels in Edo State.

5.3 Recommendations

The following are recommended:

- a) The organizations studied should endeavour to employ competent hands to handle the affairs of the organization as this will engender healthy competition among the employees.
- b) The organization should also encourage honesty and make the employees work in unity as this will make the jobs of the employees more satisfying.

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